

Guidance and input for Study Site Teams: Participatory workshop on adoption

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1 Introduction

Over the course of the first two years of the project, various work packages have investigated the question of how to facilitate the uptake of SICS from various perspectives. Our research so far has looked at the scientific literature, previous research projects and policy studies to understand how the following aspects play a role in the adoption of agricultural practices in general, and SICS in particular:

- Social factors, such as norms, trust and attitudes (WP 3);
- Policies, including EU-level, national and regional policies (WP 7);
- Advisory services (WP 8).
- Applicability of various SICS based on a range of climate, soil and land use factors (WP 6);
- Impact of SICS on profitability and sustainability (WP 2, 4, 5, 6).

We would now like to investigate the question of SICS adoption in the study sites to better understand what might promote or hinder the uptake of the SICS you are currently testing in your sites. On this basis, we would also like to identify actions for the national and (sub)regional level which have the potential of promoting SICS adoption. Please note that we use the very broad term “actions”, as these might include various types of interventions and could range from new/adapted policies to educational initiatives.

1.1 Overall approach

As already discussed at the last plenary meeting in Billund (DK), we would like to propose a **participatory workshop** to discuss these issues.¹

This document provides

1. Explanation of workshop objectives, duration, reporting and suggested participants and format of the workshop;
2. A proposed structure for the workshop including a set of guiding questions, methods and activities;
3. Background material to support Study Site Teams² in facilitating the workshop (Annex).

We would like to highlight that this guidance outlines various options for organising the workshop. Study site teams may decide the extent to which they want to discuss suggested topics with their stakeholder groups and whether they want to focus on a specific set of SICS only or on the larger topic of soil quality, protection and agriculture.

Please note that this guidance and background material may need to be adapted to your specific situation and your goals for the adoption workshop. Please do contact Zuzana (zuzana.lukakova@milieu.be) and Melanie (melanie.muro@milieu.be) if you have any questions or need our support in tailoring the suggested approach to your needs.

1.2 Workshop objectives

The general aims of the workshop are twofold:

1. **To identify and describe key barriers/enablers** facilitating the adoption of SICS, and a change towards agricultural practices beneficial to soil in general, and
2. **To identify actions at national and/or (sub)regional level** which have the potential of promoting the desired change.

Workshops can focus specifically on the SICS being tested in the study site. Alternatively, study site researchers might choose to organise a more general workshop on the question of soil quality/protection. The specific objectives you define for your event will influence the type of stakeholders you invite to the discussion, as well as the duration and format of the event.

Outputs of the workshop will feed into a deliverable detailing action at various scales of governance which could promote the adoption of SICS. Findings may also be used for

¹ This would correspond to “Stakeholder Workshop 2” in the list of stakeholder activities outlined in the Description of Action (page 11f.).

² We generally refer to Study Site Teams as there are usually a number of people working in each SoilCare study site.

producing dissemination outputs targeted at different audiences.

1.3 Workshop participants

Ideally, a workshop addressing the questions of adoption will bring together various perspectives and interests ranging from a group of actors, including farmers, policy-makers and advisory services.

Study site teams should consider whether stakeholder groups they are already working with (within the context of SoilCare or as part of their regular engagement activities) would be interested in the topic of adoption and whether it may be beneficial for the discussion to broaden the group of participants for the adoption workshop.

1.4 Workshop duration

We suggest allocating at least half a day to the discussion of adoption; this could form part of a one-day event or could be organised as a dedicated meeting. Study Site Teams

Bringing stakeholders together and asking them to take time out of their busy schedule to take part in a workshop can be challenging. Consider combining the workshop with a field day. **Field days** are scheduled to take place as part of the work programme of WP5. The purpose of these field or demonstration days is for stakeholders to visit the SoilCare experiments, and to experience and discuss their results. Please discuss the option of combining the workshop with a field day with us so we can liaise with WP5.

1.5 Workshop structure

This guidance proposes to organise the workshop in three steps. Please remember to schedule breaks between the different activities where you feel they are needed. Participants will appreciate an opportunity to chat to each other over a coffee. Also, some activities might require a change in the set-up of the room or the preparation of material (e.g. to reorganize results from one step of the process for the next step; attach new work sheets to the walls etc).

1.6 Reporting the workshop discussions and outputs

After the workshop, please send us a brief report of the workshop containing:

- the agenda;
- list of participants;
- a brief summary of the main discussion points per SICS and process step outlined.

To make this reporting task as easy as possible for you, make sure that you work in a team of at least two people, with one person taking notes and the other person facilitating the discussion. We would also advise you to take photos of all material used to structure the discussion, such as flip charts or white boards as these can be submitted with the report. Throughout this guidance, we include example tables which you could use to structure your discussions and document results. Please use these tables or adapt them as needed to report your results.

2 Proposed workshop structure/steps: Guidance for Study Site Teams

This section describes in detail the steps which we propose for the workshop.

Before you go through this process with your participants, please bear in mind that some stakeholders might be new to SoilCare or that the last meeting might have occurred a year ago. You might therefore need to reintroduce the project and, most importantly, the concept of SICS. To manage expectation, please also present the objectives of the adoption workshop, the expected outcomes and how results will be used in the project.

Please note that the aims of the adoption workshop are twofold: firstly, to identify key barriers/enablers facilitating the adoption of SICS, **and** the identification of actions which have the potential of promoting the desired change. **Study Site Teams should aim to work through all the steps of the outlined process in order to develop some feasible solutions to existing (and future) challenges to the uptake of SICS in their study site regions.**

Step 1: Describe the SICS being tested in your study site, and the expected benefits/impacts of these specific SICS for your study site.

- You can do this by compiling the information in a table (see example below) on a large piece of paper or a white board. Depending on the time available for the discussion, you may want to prefill as little or as much of the information as you want. The important point is that you review the SICS, its main characteristics and benefits together with the group of stakeholders present (see below for an example for a table structure). The point of this step is not to collect the participants' feedback on the benefits or costs of the SICS as there might be conflicting views when it comes to some

of the details; they are, of course, invited to add their own perspectives. The objective here is to introduce everyone to the SICS tested in the sites as a basis for the subsequent discussion on ways of promoting their adoption.

- ➔ If needed, you can use [Tables 1 and 2](#) (attached in the Annex) to help you prepare this step. These tables summarise the evidence available from the literature on costs, benefits etc. of the different SICS. Should you already have some first results from the field trials, these could be presented to kick off the discussion and even be accompanied by a field visit as described above.
- ➔ Please take a picture of the completed worksheet/board

Example for a table format to describe SICS tested in your site: Feel free to add those column headings that you and your stakeholder find relevant

SICS tested in site	Costs	Yield	Income	Environmental impacts (positive and negative)	...

Step 2: Identify and describe the main barriers and enablers to SICS adoption.

- ➔ To structure the discussion, we suggest you write down each SICS (described in the previous step) in the middle of a large sheet of paper or a board (see example below). Use one sheet of paper per SICS. You could start of the discussion by posing the following two simple questions:
 - *To what extent are farmers adopting this SICS (or components of it)?*
 - *What are barriers/incentives to its uptake?*
- ➔ [Table 3](#) in the Annex lists areas where we expect barriers and enablers to be identified and lists more detailed questions per category which can be used by the facilitator as prompts should participants struggle to engage in the discussion.

To help you prepare this step, you could go back to your documents from the stakeholder workshop where you selected the SICS to be tested in your study site. The question of adoption probably played a role in your discussions with the stakeholders and there might be some points which you might want to revisit with the group.

Options for organising the discussion

- Ask participants to write down their ideas on sticky notes and discuss and organise them into the categories presented in Table 3 (Annex) collectively in a group.
 - Alternatively, lead an open group discussion based around the seven categories and points presented in Table 3 (Annex). You could note down any enablers and barriers directly on the sheet of paper.
 - Depending on the number of SICS being discussed and the size of the group, stakeholders could be divided into groups and rotate around the room to work on the different SICS in turns.
- ➔ Regardless of which approach you use, you could start with a blank page with only the SICS in the middle or by organising the barriers/enablers categories as headings around the SICS.

WP6 will provide a series of eight maps reflecting important climate, soil and land use properties required for the SICS tested in your study site as well as an overall applicability map showing the combined effect (an overlay) of the eight maps. These can be used to reflect on the biophysical barriers and enablers facing the adoption of the SICS tested in your study site more widely. This could be used as an entry point for a broader discussion on barriers as participants might find it easier to start with the biophysical conditions.

Questions you could ask to discuss these layers are:

- Do you consider that the 8 individual maps and the final applicability map provide plausible information on the applicability of the action? If not, can you indicate which ones should be altered?
- Are there important bio-physical aspects – beyond the 8 currently taken into account – that you feel are missing? If so, which ones?
- Is there any regional / national data that you would be able to provide or are aware of that would improve the applicability assessment for your region or country substantially?

WP 6 will prepare a short note on the purpose and construction of the applicability layers to support Study Site Teams in this discussion.

- ➔ Please take a picture of the completed worksheet/board

- Example format for structuring barriers and enablers for SICS adoption using a generic example: Write the SICS in the middle of a piece of paper or whiteboard. You will need one paper or board per SICS (if you are discussing all SICS tested in your study site). Then list all the enablers (opportunities) on the left side and all the barriers on the right side. The table shows a generic example of what different enablers and barriers could look like.

Enablers		Barriers
Policy Positive incentives in national/EU policy	SICS selected	Economic Time/labour costs
Economic Availability of financial incentives		Knowledge Lack of knowledge of risks/farmers are unsure about risks
Biophysical conditions Favourable climate and soil conditions for application		Social/cultural factors Not well tested by farmers/unwillingness to try new options

Step 3: Identify and assess feasibility of actions to promote SICS adoption

- **A simple ranking exercise** where participants are asked to rank the factors listed on either side from least to most important could be used to develop a first understanding of relative importance. Use different coloured sticky dots and pens to ask participants to identify those barriers and enablers which are important now and those, which are most likely to change over the next 30 years. Each participant should be given 20 sticky dots (10 of each colour) and asked to identify the three most important factors affecting SICS adoption now and those, which are most likely to change over the next 30 years. They can distribute dots according to their preference, for example placing 10 dots on the most important barrier/enabler or splitting dots between several barriers/enablers. Alternatively, participants could be allowed to place up to 10 marks directly on the board if you want to use markers instead of pens. If you want to explore in more detail how some of these barriers and enablers might change over time, participants could be asked to place a post-it with their thoughts about the change next to the barrier or enabler they expect to change. The facilitator will then sum up the dots or marks to arrive at a ranking of current and future barriers and enablers.
- You can then discuss the highest ranked enablers and barriers and think about how these can be supported or overcome.

- This could be a **group discussion** where the study site team asks stakeholders to identify actions which could remove some of the barriers identified and to promote SICS uptake in their study site region. Actions could address any type of factor and could be located at different scales of governance, i.e. local, regional or national.
 - Another option would be to work in **break-out groups** focusing on individual SICS. Groups could then rotate around the room, so that each stakeholder has an opportunity to work on all SICS. Alternatively, the different groups might discuss and validate their results with the whole group.
- ➔ Ask participants to think about **actions which could remove barriers or strengthen enablers**. Here you can again consider expected changes of these factors over time – how likely are they to change and what would be the impact?
- ➔ When you are identifying actions, stakeholders should also think about their effectiveness and the feasibility of this action. Please bear in mind that it might not be feasible to remove certain barriers (such as biophysical conditions) or that some actions might be completely unrealistic.
- ➔ Questions you might ask when identifying and evaluating feasibility/effectiveness of actions to remove the identified barriers to adoption include:
- What is their effectiveness to promote adoption?
 - Are there any obstacles to implementing a specific action?
 - What are their implementation costs?
 - Do they fit the economic situation?
 - Do they fit the institutional context?
 - What is, overall, their realistic potential for successful implementation?
- ➔ The table below suggests a format for organising and capturing the discussion.
- ➔ The material listed under Step 3 in the ANNEX provides some information on how social/cultural factors, knowledge and information and the policy environment may shape adoption. For each of these sets of factors, their impact on adoption plus a subset of questions is provided. You might want to transfer these tables or parts of these tables to large sheets of paper or provide the participants with hand-outs. Depending on the initial ranking, you may focus in more detail on one or all of these categories of factors. You may of course focus on any other area, such as economic or technical barriers/enablers.
- ➔ Please take a picture of the completed worksheet/board

Example format for identifying and evaluating actions for removing barriers and supporting enablers for SICS adoption

Feasibility of implementing action (rank from 1 = not feasible to 4 = very feasible)	Effectiveness of action to promote adoption (rank from 1 = little effective to 4 = highly effective)	Actions to support enablers Identify action and describe who could implement the action and how/when in your specific condition	Enablers	SICS selected	Barriers	Actions to remove barriers Identify action and describe who could implement the action and how/when in your specific condition	Effectiveness of action to promote adoption (rank from 1 = little effective to 4 = highly effective)	Feasibility of implementing action (rank from 1 = not feasible to 4 = very feasible)
4 (very feasible); easy to implement on existing experimental farm	3 (moderately effective); might not reach many farmers	Increase farmers' knowledge in benefits to soil. Demonstration sites run by advisory services.	Social/cultural Positively received by farmers		Institutional/policy Excessive administrative rules	Simplify rules/provide guidance	4 (highly effective)	2 (somewhat feasible); would require time and political will by agencies.
		Provide trainings/workshops on e.g.machinery used Who/how/when would implement this action?	Technical Some Farmers possess required know-how		Knowledge Lack of knowledge of risks/farmers are unsure about risks	Advisory services/trainings		

3 ANNEX: MATERIALS

The materials presented here are organised by step outlined in the process guide above:

STEP 1: Description of SICS being tested in your study site, and expected benefits

The tables below are taken from the WP2 report [A preselection of soil-improving cropping systems, Executive summary Work Package 2, Revised version 02-02-2017](#) (Table 1 can be found on page 34 and Table 2 on page 28).

Table 1: List of promising general SICS

Component	Expected impact
Crop rotation	Improves crop productivity, soil biodiversity and system sustainability; decreases need for pesticides and risk of erosion
Green manures, cover crops, catch crops	Improves SOM content, soil structure, soil biodiversity, nutrient use efficiency; decreases nutrient leaching, run-off, erosion
Integrated nutrient management	Improves crop productivity, soil nutrient status and resource use efficiency;
Enhanced efficiency irrigation	Improves crop productivity and resource use efficiency; minimizes risks of salinization and desertification
Controlled drainage	Improves crop productivity and resource use efficiency; minimizes the risk of waterlogging
Reduced tillage	Reduces energy cost and may enhance SOM content and soil structure; may increase the need for herbicides/ pesticides
Integrated pest management	Improves crop productivity and resource use efficiency; minimizes the loss of biodiversity.
Smart weed control	Improves crop productivity and resource use efficiency; may decrease the need for herbicides
Smart residue management	Reduces evaporation and soil temperature; may increase/decrease the success of germination
Controlled trafficking	Reduces energy cost and the risk of soil compaction
Integrated landscape management	Improves biodiversity and cropping systems sustainability

Table 2: Preliminary assessment of components of SICS: productivity and sustainability indicators.

Components of SICS	Crop yield & quality	Soil quality	Farm income	Resource use efficiency	Environmental impacts
Monocultures (reference)	0	0	0	0	0
Crop rotation	+	+	+	+	+
Wide rotations (1:6)	+	+	+	++	++
Narrow rotations (1:3)	+/-	+/-	++	+/-	+/-
+ root crops (1:2)	++	-	++	+/-	-
+ legumes(1:3)	+	+	+	++	+
+ allelopathic plants (1:4)	-/+	+	-/+	+/-	0
+ cover crops(1:1)	+	+	-/+	+	+
+ intercropping	++	+	+/-	++	+
+ green manures (1:1)	++	++	+/-	+	+

Components of SICS	Crop yield & quality	Soil quality	Farm income	Resource use efficiency	Environmental impacts
+ phytoremediation	+/-	+	+/-	+/-	+
Fallow/set-aside (1:6)	--	+	--	--	-
No fertilization (reference)	0	0	0	0	0
Fertilization	+	+	++	+	--
Balanced fertilization	++	+	++	+	-
Precision (split) fertilization	++	+	++	+	-
Manure application	+	++	++	+	-
Compost application	+	++	++	+	-
Biofertilizers (micro-organisms)	+	+	+	-/+	-
Liming	+	++	+	+	+
No irrigation (reference)	0	0	0	0	0
Irrigation	++	+	++	+	-
Flood irrigation	+	+/-	+	+/-	--
Sprinkling irrigation	+	+	+	+/-	-
Drip irrigation	++	+	++	+	+/-
Fertigation	++	+	++	+	+/-
No drainage (reference)	0	0	0	0	0
Drainage	+	+	+	+	+/-
Tile drainage	+	+	+	+	+/-
Controlled drainage	+	+	+	+	+
No tillage (reference)	0	0	0	0	0
Conventional tillage	+	+/-	+/-	-	-
Reduced tillage	+	+	+/-	+/-	-/+
Deep ploughing	+/-	+	+/-	+/-	+/-
Subsoiling	+/-	+	+/-	+/-	+/-
No pest management (reference)	0	0	0	0	0
Chemical pest management	++	-	++	+	-
Biological control	++	0	++	+	0
No weed control (reference)	0	0	0	0	0
Conventional weed control	++	-	++	+	-
Mechanical weed control	++	-/+	+	-/+	-/+
No mulching (no reference)	0	0	0	0	0
Residue mulching	+	+	+	+	+
Plastic mulching	++	-/+	+	+	-/+
No controlled trafficking (reference)	0	0	0	0	0
Controlled trafficking	+	+	+/-	+	+
No landscape management (reference)	0	0	0	0	0
Landscape management	0	0	+	+/-	+
Hedges, riparian zones	0	0	+	+/-	+
Agroforestry	-/+	+/-	+/-	+	+
Crop – livestock integration	+	+	+	++	+
Terracing, contouring	+	+	+/-	+	+

STEP 2: Identification/description of the main barriers and enablers to SICS adoption.

Facilitators of and barriers for adoption can be broadly grouped into the following broad categories:

Table 3: Barriers and enablers for SICS adoption

Economic (farm/market) conditions	<p>Market conditions might be favourable or not. Market conditions might include prices, supply chain arrangements and possible food assurance schemes/protocols, the role of private sector actors, consumer preferences and consumption patterns.</p> <p>New practices might not seem profitable or come with high investment and labour costs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>What are the costs versus the benefits of using the SICS?</i> • <i>Are there costs preventing its uptake? Explain what the costs are (e.g. new machinery, more labour)?</i> • <i>Are there economic risks involved in using the SICS? Explain what the risks are (e.g. uncertain effect on yield/quality, volatile markets, loss of contract)?</i> • <i>Are there any economic incentives for adopting the SICS?</i>
Biophysical conditions	<p>Climate and soils might be favourable or unfavorable.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>What are the biophysical and crop type barriers stopping the adoption of the SICS?</i>
Technical barriers	<p>Techniques/practices might not be sufficiently tested yet or required acquisition of new skills/training.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>How difficult is the SICS? Are there agronomic/technical risks involved?</i> • <i>Does the SICS require extra skills, knowledge, education, training? For the advisors and/or for the farmers?</i>
Knowledge / information	<p>Farmers may not be sufficiently informed about soil improving practices/cropping systems or the extent to which the technique/practice might be applicable to them.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Are farmers aware of the SICS? Do they understand the potential benefits?</i> • <i>Is it easy to access the relevant information? Does it cost anything?</i> • <i>Can advisory/ extension services effectively support farmers with the adoption of SICS?</i> • <i>Can farmers visit demonstration sites, or do they have the opportunity to try it out on the farm?</i>
Social/cultural factors	<p>Farmers are unwilling of testing new practices and techniques; limited promotion of SICS by farmer organisations.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Do personal motivations and values prevent uptake by farmers?</i> • <i>Do cultural aspects (e.g. traditional ways of doing things, accepted behaviours, habitual attitudes) prevent uptake?</i> • <i>Are there supportive social networks, peer support if farmers want to learn about or uptake up the SICS?</i>
Institutional and policy environment	<p>Policies (including regulation, economic, voluntary and information instruments) hinder the uptake of SICS by subsidising or promoting other practices.</p>

STEP 3: Step 3: Identification/feasibility of actions to promote SICS adoption

The material presented below first provides some background information for workshop facilitators highlighting the relationship between the different types of adoption factors and SICS uptake. This is followed by a set of questions for the specific set of adoption factors.

Social/cultural factors

As a highly social species, our actions are influenced by those around us, just as we influence those close to us like our friends and family. The networks that we are connected to affect how we and our society functions. For example, knowing the right kind of people can make it easier for someone to find a job, which benefits the individual. Equally, working together on a problem with trusted networks such as close friends can make the process more fruitful than working with strangers that you don't trust, which benefits the group.

The benefits that we as individuals and society receive as a result of social interactions is called "social capital" and this is thought to be made up of a number of factors.

- Trust: we work best with the people we trust, and not trusting someone can severely affect our relationship. Trusting the information someone gives can influence whether we decide to act on that information.
- Norms: norms are the commonly-held way in which we act in a society. For instance, there is a norm for Brits to make small-talk about the weather, just as there's a norm for them to queue.
- Connectedness: who we associate with affects us. If we only associate with people similar to ourselves, we tend not to pick up new skills and information as quickly than if we associate with people who are different to us.

Questions/Exercise

One important question could be to ask participants who they think are the most important sources of information (e.g. other farmers, advisory services, farming magazines, websites etc.) for farmers when farmers want to learn new things. This could be done as a group discussion with the whole group if there are fewer than 8 people, or in a few smaller groups of, say, 4-6 people if the group is larger. The discussion could start out by getting participants to talk about which these sources of information are and have the note taker list them on a flip chart. Then it would be useful to get them to rank them from most to least likely to act on the information they receive from each of these sources which would be a good indication of whether they trust that information and the source.

Knowledge/information

Advisers need access to evidence and tools from research to formulate credible and tailored advice for farmers (e.g. on nutrient and SOM management) particularly with respect to the co-benefits and trade-offs of different or combinations of soil management options under varying scenarios

Build technical capacity in advisory services this is key for soil management particularly in advisers' field assessment soil data and soil analysis interpretation skills in the context of nutrient management and soil health indicators

Improve **links between research institutions and advisory services** to encourage integration of scientific and practitioner soil knowledge as part of this capacity building Recognise the new facilitating role of advisers and provide **training in initiating fostering and brokering farmer-centred networks** interested in soil management

Build on and support **existing farmer networks and communities of practice where adviser researcher and farmer are already learning and experimenting together on** soil management

Raise adviser awareness about the value of soil and its multiple functions and threats to shift the focus away from meeting EU CAP regulatory requirements or single functions

Build capacity **in the farming community**. Supporting innovative experimental and peer to peer learning should be complemented with education and **awareness raising** about soil among all farmers particularly given the demand-led nature of many advisory services.

NB It is acknowledged that the terms **adviser, researcher and farmer** are simplistic and not always mutually exclusive they are used here as a 'short cut'

Questions/Exercise

Please note that there is not one definition of advisor/advisory services. WP8 colleagues use the following definition: advisory services can be defined as sets of organisations that support and facilitate people engaged in agricultural production to solve problems and to obtain information, skills, and technologies, by enabling farmers to co-produce farm-level solutions by establishing service relationships with advisers.

If knowledge/information is one of the key areas where participants identify barriers, there are two options for identifying actions for improving the situation: 1) present a summary of the key points in the table and ask stakeholders to identify the most relevant actions for your study site/country; or 2) start with a blank piece of paper and use the table as guidance for the facilitator.

The following questions can be used to guide the discussion:

1. **What is** advisers' expertise for:
 - soil physical assessment, soil data and soil analysis interpretation skills in the context of nutrient management and soil health indicators,
 - recommending appropriate SICS?

- if poor how do we **build capacity in advisory services**? Can you give specific examples of effective training/upskilling?
- 2. **What is adviser awareness** about the value of soil? How can the focus be shifted away from meeting EU CAP regulatory requirements, or single functions towards SICS?
- 3. **Who** should we target for dissemination about SICS (who are the main influencers?) and what is the best way of sharing this information with them?

Impacts of EU policies, instruments and measures on SICS adoption³

Policies/instruments	CAP			WFD	Birds and Habitats Directives	Sewage Sludge Directive	Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive	Fertilisers Directive
	Greening	Cross-compliance	RDP	Nitrates Directive				
SICS								
Green manures, cover crops, catch crops	Cover crops and catch crops are eligible measures under EFAs.	No directly relevant standards	Rural development measures can be used to cover transaction costs associated with cover crops i.e. seeds and increased use of machinery, targeted cover crops identified in SoilCare could be included in an agri-environmental-climate payment (Pillar 2).	No directly relevant standards. However voluntary codes of Good Agricultural Practice (GAP) include requirements for crop rotations, soil winter cover, and catch crops to prevent nitrate leaching and run-off during wet seasons.	No directly relevant standards	No directly relevant standards	Cover crops and catch crops are included under measures relating to integrated pest management and can be included in MS action plans for reducing pesticide use.	No directly relevant standards
Crop rotation	Although the <i>Crop Diversification</i> greening measure incentivizes increasing the number of crops in agricultural holdings, it does not specifically address crop rotations. The measure permanent	No directly relevant standards	Costs associated with crop rotation can potentially be covered by AECM.	No directly relevant standards. However voluntary GAP codes include requirements for crop rotations, soil winter cover, and catch crops to prevent nitrate leaching and run-off during wet seasons.	No directly relevant standards	No directly relevant standards	Crop rotation can be beneficial for pest management and are included under measures relating to integrated pest management and can be included in MS action plans for reducing pesticide use.	No directly relevant standards

³ Not directly relevant for study sites in CH and NO.

Policies/instruments	CAP			WFD	Birds and Habitats Directives	Sewage Sludge Directive	Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive	Fertilisers Directive
	Greening	Cross-compliance	RDP	Nitrates Directive				
	pasture can potentially limit long crop rotations by limiting the possibility to plough up pasture that has been established for > 5 years.							
Integrated nutrient management	No directly relevant standards	Cross-compliance with the Statutory Management Requirements (SMR) on Nitrates Directives directly impacts on farmers management of nutrients.	RDP measures can be used to finance manure storage, small scale bio refineries to reduce GHG/Ammonia emissions, and information and awareness building relating to nutrient management and nutrient runoff/leaching	Directly impact on farmers nutrient management by establishing maximum levels of nitrogen applied, periods and landscapes where application of nitrogen based fertilisers is inappropriate, designation of Nitrate Vulnerable Zones (NVZ) and GAPs relating to reducing nitrogen runoff such as cover, catch crops, and buffer strips.	HD Annex II species may require more stringent conditions to reach favourable conservation status than the ones necessary to achieve good ecological status including nutrient levels.	Sewage sludge is a cost-efficient source nutrient. SSD sets limits for land-based applications and establishes maximum levels of pollutants in sewage sludge (although most MS have stricter standards compared to SSD).	No directly relevant standards	Does not directly affect nutrient management but provides stable operating environment for trade in fertilisers. The new fertilisers directive is expected to make organic fertilisers and products that improve uptake of nutrients more readily accessible for farmers.
Enhanced efficiency irrigation	No directly relevant standards	No directly relevant standards	RDP measures relating to physical investments can be used for investments in more efficient irrigation systems	No directly relevant standards, but have indirect impacts relating to ensuring sufficient quality and	No directly relevant standards	No directly relevant standards	Annex III includes use of balanced fertilisation, liming and irrigation/drainage practices in general	No directly relevant standards

Policies/instruments	CAP			WFD	Birds and Habitats Directives	Sewage Sludge Directive	Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive	Fertilisers Directive
	Greening	Cross-compliance	RDP	Nitrates Directive				
			and/or drainage systems.	quantity of water.			list of practices for Integrated Pest Management.	
Controlled drainage	No directly relevant standards	No directly relevant standards	RDP measures relating to physical investments can be used for investments in more efficient irrigation systems and/or drainage systems.					
Reduced tillage	No directly relevant standards	No directly relevant standards for reduced tillage, but would satisfy GAECs for improving soil organic matter and reducing soil erosion	RDP investment measure can be used to cover costs associated with specific machinery required for zero tillage or low tillage practices.	No directly relevant standards, but technique reduces need for application of nitrogen-based fertilisers and could be used as strategy for reduction of nitrogen leaching especially in designated NZVs.	No directly relevant standards, but reduced tillage systems can be beneficial for farmland bird population and habitats.	No directly relevant standards	Annex III includes use conservation agriculture i.e. reduced tillage in list of general practices for Integrated Pest Management.	No directly relevant standards
Integrated pest management	No directly relevant standards, although several measures that qualify as EFAs could also be part of integrated pest management strategies	No directly relevant standards	No directly relevant standards	No directly relevant standards		No directly relevant standards	Integrated Pest Management is one of the key features of the regulation and stresses that Member States shall establish or support the establishment of necessary conditions for the implementation of	No directly relevant standards

Policies/instruments	CAP			WFD	Birds and Habitats Directives	Sewage Sludge Directive	Sustainable Use of Pesticides Directive	Fertilisers Directive
	Greening	Cross-compliance	RDP	Nitrates Directive				
							integrated pest management	
Smart weed control	No directly relevant standards	No directly relevant standards	No directly relevant standards	No directly relevant standards	No directly relevant standards	No directly relevant standards	Integrated Pest Management includes different measure to control weeds and reduce the use of herbicides	No directly relevant standards
Smart residue management	No directly relevant standards	Cross-compliance includes GAECs on improving soil organic matter and a ban on burning of stubble, but does not include measures per se on residue management	No directly relevant standards	No directly relevant standards, although residue management is part of the broader principles of Integrated pest management described in annex III of the directive				

Impacts of national and regional policy instruments and measures on SICS adoption: Overview of key policies, Loddington (UK)

Policy name	Scale	EU or MS level	Impact on SICS	Description of policy
CAP GAEC Cross-compliance Standards	National	EU	Plant cover; Agroforestry; Nutrient management; Tillage management; Machine & traffic	'Cross compliance' is a set of rules which farmers and land managers must follow on their holding if they are claiming rural payments. The cross compliance is set in the Common Agriculture Policy Regulations 2014 and further explained in the Guide to cross compliance in England 2017. Schedule 2 of the Common Agriculture Policy Regulations 2014 requires restoration of a footpath or bridleway after ploughing and prohibits crop and specified vegetation burning (section 2). The Schedule further requires the farmers to cover the soil with crops or other vegetation, although exceptions are allowed (section 3); maintain green cover,

Policy name	Scale	EU or MS level	Impact on SICS	Description of policy
			management; Mulching	prevent erosion and refrain from applying fertilisers or pesticides to land near watercourses and hedgerow, although exemptions are allowed (sections 4 and 5).
The Guide to Cross-compliance in England 2017	Regional	EU	Plant cover; Agroforestry; Nutrient management; Tillage management; Machine & traffic management; Mulching	The Guide contains the 'Good Agricultural and Environmental Conditions' (GAECs) which cover, inter alia, environment, climate change and good agricultural condition of land. GAEC 4 establishes that farmers must take all reasonable steps to protect soil by having a minimum soil cover all year around unless there is an agronomic justification for not doing so, or where establishing a cover would conflict with requirements under GAEC 5 that causes soil erosion. GAEC 5 requires measures to be put into place to limit soil and bankside erosion (cropping practices and structures, vehicles, trailers and machinery). GAEC 6 prohibits farmers from burning cereal straw or cereal stubble or certain crop residues, with the aim of maintain the level of organic matter in soil.
CAP Rural Development Programme 2014 - 2020	National	EU	Intercropping, crop rotations	The Rural Development Programme (RDP) for England was formally adopted by the European Commission in 2015. It outlines England's priorities for using the €4 billion available from 2014-2020 (national and EU contributions). The main objective of the RDP is better management of natural resources and the wider adoption of farming practices which are climate friendly. Soil degradation has been estimated to cost the economy £0.9-1.4bn per year in England and Wales (p. 108). Soil erosion and acidification and climate change have been recognised as an important issue in England (p. 37 - 39). To tackle these issues, RDP's Focus area 4C focuses on preventing soil erosion and improving soil management. One of the measures concerns crop diversification (p. 396); buffer strips on cultivated land (p. 397); winter cover crops (p. 398); etc.
Countryside Stewardship	Regional	EU	Plant cover, Landscape Management, Integrated Management.	Countryside Stewardship (CS) provides financial incentives for land managers to look after their environment through activities such as: conserving and restoring wildlife habitats; flood risk management; woodland creation and management; reducing widespread water pollution from agriculture; keeping the character of the countryside; preserving features important to the history of the rural landscape and encouraging educational access. The scheme is open to all eligible farmers, woodland owners, foresters and other land managers in England and is suitable for many types of land use (for example conventional and organic farmland, coastal areas, uplands and woodlands). It is a competitive scheme with application scored against local priority targets to maximise environmental benefit.
Pesticides Control legislation	national	EU	Pest management	The Control of Pesticides Regulations (1986, as amended in 1997) provides a high-level regulatory setting with details of pesticides subject to control and a system of approvals required for supply, storage and use. In addition, the Plant Protection Products (Sustainable Use) Regulations 2012 transpose Directive on sustainable use of pesticides. Users of plant protection products/pesticides are required to take all reasonable precautions to protect, inter alia, soil.
Campaign for the Farmed Environment	Regional	MS	Integrated management, Pest Management, Landscape, Plant	The Campaign for the Farmed Environment (CFE) is an industry-led initiative encouraging voluntary management that will benefit the environment, whilst ensuring efficient and profitable food production. CFE guidance includes voluntary measures and best practice actions to benefit wildlife and to protect natural resources on farmland, and promoting

Policy name	Scale	EU or MS level	Impact on SICS	Description of policy
			cover & Nutrient Management	resource use efficiency is a natural progression for CFE. It is a partnership of 15 farming and Environmental Organisations working together.

Questions/Exercise

1. *Do you think that SICS tested in your site fit in with existing policies and instruments?*
2. *Do existing policies place requirements or incentives on farmers which would hamper/promote SICS uptake? What factors would need to change to ensure effectiveness of existing policies in terms of SICS adoption?*
3. *Do you think that we need to change existing policies/ instruments and how?*